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Imprints of scalar mediated NSI on long baseline experiments

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Abstract

The experimental observation of the phenomena of neutrino oscillations, which essentially confirms non-zero masses of neutrinos, has opened a new sector to explore physics beyond the Standard Model. The models describing new-physics phenomena often come with some unknown interactions of neutrinos termed as Non Standard Interactions (NSIs). It is highly important and interesting to explore the impact of NSIs in the ongoing and upcoming neutrino oscillations experiments for precise measurement of the oscillation parameters. In this work, we have probed the impact of a scalar-mediated NSI in the long baseline sector, focussing at the three upcoming long-baseline (LBL) experiments: (DUNE, T2HK and T2HKK). The effects of SNSI appear as a medium-dependent corrections to the neutrino mass term. Its contribution scales linearly with matter density, making LBL experiments among the most suitable candidates for probing such effects. We show that the presence of SNSI may significantly impact the oscillation probabilities as well as the event rates at the detectors and the χ^2 -sensitivities of δ_{CP} measurements of the experiments. We also show that, a synergy among the LBL experiments (DUNE+T2HK, DUNE+T2HKK), which may offer a better capability of constraining the SNSI parameters as well as an improved sensitivity towards CP-violation.

1 Introduction

The phenomenon of neutrino (ν) oscillations has opened up a new avenue in the field of particle physics, confirming the existence of physics beyond the standard model (BSM) of particle physics. Various exceptional experiments conducted globally are currently focused on achieving enhanced precision in measuring the mixing parameters, determining the mass hierarchy, investigating the leptonic CP violation and establishing the absolute neutrino mass scale. The BSM models for explaining mass and oscillation, inherently carry new particles, interactions and violation of fundamental symmetries. One such non-standard interaction (NSI) is the coupling of neutrinos with a scalar particle [5, 3, 8], namely scalar NSI (SNSI). The general idea of NSI was first proposed by Wolfenstein, as a possible explanation for neutrino flavor change [10]. Although oscillations has now been established as the primary cause of flavor change, NSIs are manifested as subdominant matter effects to ν -oscillation. These subtle effects have shown a substantial impact on the precision measurement of neutrino oscillation parameters. Here, we focus mainly on the effects of SNSI on the CP measurement sensitivities at DUNE [2] and T2HK [1]. We have also explored the unique possibility to constraint the absolute ν -mass via ν -oscillation experiments in presence of SNSI.

2 Formalism of scalar NSI

In standard model, ν 's interact via CC or NC weak interactions mediated by W^\pm & Z^0 boson. NC-interactions being flavor blind do not contribute to oscillations. Therefore, the SM Lagrangian for matter effect in neutrino oscillations can be written as,

$$\mathcal{L}_{CC}^{eff} = -\frac{4G_F}{\sqrt{2}} [\bar{\nu}_e(p_3)\gamma_\mu P_L \nu_e(p_2)] [\bar{e}(p_1)\gamma^\mu P_L e(p_4)]. \quad (1)$$

Here, G_F represents the Fermi coupling constant, $P_L = (1 - \gamma_5)/2$ is the left chiral projection operator and p_i 's are momenta of the incoming & outgoing states. The effective Hamiltonian in this case is,

$$\mathcal{H}_{matter} = \frac{MM^\dagger}{2E_\nu} \pm V_{SI}, \quad (2)$$

where $V_{SI} = \text{diag}(\sqrt{2}G_F n_e, 0, 0)$, with n_e representing the electron number density.

In BSM physics, apart from CC and NC weak interactions, there may be new coupling of neutrinos mediated by vector or scalar particles. The effective Lagrangian for scalar-mediated neutrino-fermion interaction is [5],

$$\mathcal{L}_{eff}^s \propto y_f y_{\alpha\beta} [\bar{\nu}_\alpha(p_3)\nu_\beta(p_2)] [\bar{f}(p_1)f(p_4)], \quad (3)$$

where $\alpha, \beta \in (e, \mu, \tau)$ are the three active ν flavors, f (\bar{f}) denotes matter fermions (anti-fermions), y_f represents the Yukawa coupling of scalar ϕ with environmental fermions f & $y_{\alpha\beta}$ is the Yukawa couplings of ϕ with ν 's. This leads to a correction of the mass term in the Dirac equation.

$$\bar{\nu}_\beta \left[i\partial_\mu \gamma^\mu + \left(M_{\beta\alpha} + \frac{\sum_f n_f y_f y_{\alpha\beta}}{m_\phi^2} \right) \right] = 0, \quad (4)$$

where n_f signifies the number density of environmental fermions. As a consequence, the SNSI appears in the effective Hamiltonian as a perturbation to the ν mass term, which can be expressed as,

$$\mathcal{H}_{SNSI} \equiv \frac{M_{eff} M_{eff}^\dagger}{2E_\nu} \pm V_{SI}. \quad (5)$$

M_{eff} has the form $M + \delta M$ with contributions both from the genuine mass term (M) and SNSI correction ($\delta M \equiv \sum_f n_f y_f y_{\alpha\beta} / m_\phi^2$). We have parameterized δM as shown in [5, 8, 7].

$$\delta M \equiv \sqrt{|\Delta m_{31}^2|} \begin{pmatrix} \eta_{ee} & \eta_{e\mu} & \eta_{\mu\tau} \\ \eta_{\mu e} & \eta_{\mu\mu} & \eta_{\mu\tau} \\ \eta_{\tau e} & \eta_{\mu\tau} & \eta_{\tau\tau} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (6)$$

Here the $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$ parameters quantify the strength of SNSI. In order to preserve the hermiticity of the Hamiltonian, the diagonal parameters are real & the off-diagonal parameters are complex with the form, $\eta_{\alpha\beta} = |\eta_{\alpha\beta}| e^{i\phi_{\alpha\beta}}$. One very interesting consequence of SNSI is its dependence on absolute ν -mass [9] due to the introduction of the cross terms $M\delta M^\dagger$ & $M^\dagger\delta M$ in the Hamiltonian. This gives rise to the exclusive possibility of probing absolute ν -mass through oscillation experiments. In our work, we have leveraged the absolute mass dependence of SNSI to constrain the lightest ν -mass at DUNE.

3 Methodology

We have used the GLoBES [6] framework to simulate the long-baseline experiments. The effective Hamiltonian in the presence of SNSI can be added to the GLoBES framework to study its impact on the numerically calculated probabilities. The best-fit values of the parameters used for GLoBES simulation are tabulated in 1. A statistical χ^2 can also be defined in the GLoBES

Parameters	Values	Parameters	Values
$\theta_{12} [^\circ]$	34.51	L[km]	1300
$\theta_{13} [^\circ]$	8.44	δ_{CP}	$-\pi/2$
$\theta_{23} [^\circ]$	47	Hierarchy	Normal
$\Delta m_{21}^2 [10^{-5} eV^2]$	7.56	$\Delta m_{31}^2 [10^{-3} eV^2]$	2.55

Table 1: Best fit values of neutrino mixing parameters [4].

framework that can quantify the physics sensitivities of different measurements. The statistical χ^2 can be defined as,

$$\chi^2 \equiv \min_{\eta} \sum_i \sum_j \frac{[N_{true}^{i,j} - N_{test}^{i,j}]^2}{N_{true}^{i,j}}, \quad (7)$$

Here, $N_{true}^{i,j}$ ($N_{test}^{i,j}$) defines the number of true (test) events in $(i, j)^{th}$ bin.

4 Results & Discussion

We have explored the impact of diagonal SNSI elements on the CP measurement sensitivities for two long-baseline experiments- DUNE and T2HK. We have also explored the possibility of constraining the lightest mass of ν 's in the presence of SNSI at DUNE. In figure 1, we have explored the impact of η_{ee} , $\eta_{\mu\mu}$ and $\eta_{\tau\tau}$ on the CP-Violation (CPV) and CP-Precision sensitivities at DUNE taking only one parameter at a time. The red solid line represents the standard case i.e. no SNSI. The positive (negative) values of $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$ are represented by the solid (dashed) lines. And the 5σ (3σ) CL are represented by the magenta (green) dashed lines. In the top panels, we have shown the impact of $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$ on the CP-Violation sensitivities. We observe that CPV sensitivities enhance (suppress) in the presence of positive (negative) η_{ee} . In all the cases, we see that negative values of $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$ suppresses the sensitivities. In the bottom panels, we have shown the impact of $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$ on the CP-Precision sensitivities. We have fixed the true δ_{CP}

Figure 1: CP-Violation (top) and CP-Precision (bottom) sensitivity in the presence of η_{ee} (left panel), $\eta_{\mu\mu}$ (middle panel) and $\eta_{\tau\tau}$ (right panel) at DUNE.

Figure 2: CP Violation sensitivities in the presence of η_{ee} for DUNE (left panel), T2HK (middle panel) and DUNE+T2HK (right panel).

value at $-\pi/2$. For all positive diagonal $\eta_{\alpha\beta}$ parameters, the CP-precision sensitivity enhances for complete δ_{CP} space, whereas the sensitivity suppresses for negative values.

In figure 2, we have explored how the presence of SNSI element η_{ee} can affect the CP-Violation sensitivities at two different experiments i.e. T2HK and DUNE. We have also considered the synergy of T2HK and DUNE experiments. The solid red line showcases the standard case i.e. $\eta_{ee} = 0$. For all the cases, we see an enhancement (suppression) in the CPV sensitivities for positive (negative) η_{ee} values. We observe that the synergy leads to an improvement in the sensitivity towards CP-Violation.

In figure 3, we have explored the impact of SNSI on the neutrino oscillation probabilities for varying lightest neutrino mass at DUNE. We have considered the SNSI elements η_{ee} (left panel), $\eta_{\mu\mu}$ (middle panel) and $\eta_{\tau\tau}$ (right panel). In the top (bottom) panels, we have considered the normal (inverted) hierarchy as the true hierarchy. We see that the presence of SNSI elements

can significantly alter the ν -oscillation probabilities for both hierarchies. In figure 4, we have

Figure 3: Appearance probabilities for varying lightest ν -mass for normal (top panel) and inverted (bottom panel) in the presence of η_{ee} (left), $\eta_{\mu\mu}$ (middle) and $\eta_{\tau\tau}$ (right) at DUNE.

set constraints on the lightest ν mass for normal (top) & inverted (bottom) hierarchy at DUNE. We have considered the SNSI elements η_{ee} (left panel), $\eta_{\mu\mu}$ (middle panel) and $\eta_{\tau\tau}$ (right panel) parameters taking only one at a time. We have varied the lightest ν mass in accordance with the cosmological bound on $\sum m_i < 0.12 eV$. It is seen that the lightest ν mass can be better constrained for normal hierarchy in comparison to inverted hierarchy.

5 Summary and Conclusion

The study of non-standard effects and their impact on different neutrino experiments is important as it can affect the physics sensitivities of these experiments. The presence of SNSI is seen to affect the neutrino oscillation probabilities. This results in enhancement/suppression of sensitivities in the measurement of δ_{CP} . The synergy of T2HK and DUNE is shown to improve the CP-measurement sensitivities. The direct dependence of ν -oscillation probabilities on the absolute neutrino mass is probed to put bounds on the lightest ν -mass.

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Figure 4: Constraint on the lightest ν -mass in the presence of η_{ee} (left), $\eta_{\mu\mu}$ (middle) and $\eta_{\tau\tau}$ (right) for normal (top) and inverted (bottom) hierarchy at DUNE.

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